

Table 1. Sensitivity of MAb-ELISA in the detection of Xoo. ^a

Technique	Sensitivity at given strain concentration (cells/ml)						
	10 ⁶	10 ⁵	10 ⁴	10 ³	10 ²	10 ¹	PBS(check)
DAS-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
DAS-ABC-ELISA	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
ID-ELISA	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
ID-ABC-ELISA	+	+	+	+	-	-	-

^a + = positive = no. OD₅₅₀ is twice that of check. - = negative.

Table 2. Specificity of MAb-ELISA in the detection of Xoo.

Technique	Specificity							
	Xoo	<i>X.o. pv. oryzicola</i>	<i>X.c. pv. malvacearum</i>	<i>X.c. pv. campestris</i>	<i>E. carotovora</i> subsp. <i>carotovora</i>	<i>P. solana-cearum</i>	<i>C. sepedonicum</i>	<i>A. tumefaciens</i>
DAS-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DAS-ABC-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ID-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ID-ABC-ELISA	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The cultures of Xoo were diluted into different concentrations (cells/ml) and tested using four methods. The sensitiv-

ity of ABC-MAb-ELISA was higher than that of ELISA; ID-ABC-ELISA had the highest (Table 1). In our experi-

ments, the sensitivity of ID-ELISA was higher than that of DAS-ELISA.

We detected some important plant pathogenic bacteria belonging to different genera or species. Negative reactions were observed on *Elwinia carotovoru* subsp. *carotovora*, *Pseudomonas solanacearum*, *Corynebacterium sepedonicum*, and *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. We also observed negative reactions on the same species but of different pathogenic types: *X. campestris* pv. *campestris*, *X. campestris* pv. *malvacearum*, and *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* (Table 2).

Our experiment showed that by adding the biotin-avidin system to the ELISA, the sensitivity of reaction could be improved without changing specificity. ABC-MAb-ELISA will be useful in detecting Xoo. □

Distribution of sheath rot (ShR) in six agroclimatic zones of Assam, India

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ShR was confined to the rice-growing areas of Cachar district in Assam during the early 1980s, but it has gradually spread to other regions. We surveyed 17 rice-growing districts representing the state's six agroclimatic zones to better understand the current status of the disease. Fields planted to different cultivars of transplanted rice located along the national highways were inspected at booting stage during the 1989 and 1990 wet seasons (Jul-Oct). We assessed all the hills in a 1-m² area at each site. ShR incidence was calculated as number of infected tillers divided by total tillers × 100.

The highest incidences of ShR were in Karimganj and Cachar districts of the Barak Valley zone (see table). Lowest incidences (4%) were in the two districts of the hill zone. No zone, however, was disease-free. Jaya and IR20 had higher infection incidence than other commonly cultivated rice. □

Sheath rot incidence in 6 agroclimatic zones of Assam, India, 1989-90.

Agroclimatic zone	District	Fields surveyed (no.)	Range of incidence (%)	Agroclimatic zone	District	Fields surveyed (no.)	Range of incidence (%)
Upper Brahmaputra Valley	Dibrugarh	4	21-30	Hill zone	Karbi Anglong	4	<5
	Sibsagar	3	11-20		North Cachar	3	<5
	Jorhat	4	31-40	North Bank Plain	Lakhimpur	3	31-40
	Golaghat	2	11-20		Sonitpur	2	11-20
Central Brahmaputra Valley	Nowgong	2	11-20	Darag	41-10		
	Marigaon	2	11-20	Barak Valley	Karimganj Cachar	4	>50
Lower Brahmaputra Valley	Kamrup	3	11-20			3	41-50
	Borpeta	2	1-10		Total	52	
	Kokrajhar	4	11-20				
	Goalpara	3	1-10				

Chemical control of neck blast (BI) through granular fungicides

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is a serious constraint to the production of scented rice in Haryana. We evaluated granular fungicides pyroquilon, chlobenthiazone, and IBP and a soil application of a recommended spray fungicide (edifenphos). Susceptible

cultivar Pakistani Basmati was transplanted in Jul 1986. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 5- × 3-m² plots. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Fungicides were broadcast at disease initiation prior to panicle initiation. We applied pyroquilon, chlobenthiazone, and IBP at 30 and 40 kg/ha and edifenphos at 5 liters of the formulated product in 60 kg sand/ha. Disease incidence was recorded as the percent infected panicles in 250 randomly selected tillers/plot 20 d after the last application of fungicide.

Effect of fungicides on neck B1 incidence and yield of Pakistani Basmati.

Treatment	Rate of application/ha (on formulation basis)	Disease incidence (%)	Disease control over check (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase in yield over check (%)
Pyroquilon	30 kg DI + 40 kg PI ^a	12.7	69.8	3.2	16.3
Chlobenthiazole	30 kg DI + 40 kg PI	6.0	85.7	3.1	13.9
IBP	30 kg DI + 40 kg PI	29.3	30.2	2.9	4.0
Edifenphos	5 liters in 60 kg sand DI + 5 liters in 60 kg sand PI	18.0	57.1	3.0	7.1
Check	-	42.0	-	2.8	-
LSD 0.05		4.7			

^aDI = at disease initiation. PI = at panicle initiation.

Rice yellow dwarf (RYD) disease in Assam, India

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RYD symptoms have been noticed in rainfed lowland, transplanted autumn rice (Mar/Apr to Aug) in the Barak Valley Zone of Assam since 1989. Plants showed pronounced stunting, profuse tillering, uniform, pale yellow leaves, and lack of panicle development. Panicles were short with chaffy grains if they emerged. Similar symptoms were observed in ratoon crops.

We observed 7.50 indigenous entries from the autumn rice germplasm collection of RARS during 1991. Of these, 179 showed RYD symptoms, with 3-12% of the plants infected. Recommended varieties—DR92, Cauvery, Rasi, Culture 1, and Akashi—exhibited similar symptoms.

RYD had never been reported before in this zone and therefore had to be confirmed. We conducted transmission studies using green leafhopper (GLH) during 1991 kharif. We gave 2d- and 3d-instar GLH nymphs acquisition access feeding for 24 h on apparently RYD-infected Cauvery plants. After 30 d of incubation, the viruliferous insects were allowed inoculation access feeding for 24 h on 11-d-old seedlings for each variety. Visible symptoms of RYD appeared in all the test varieties 22-27 d after inoculation.

Spraying RYD-infected plants with a 250-ppm solution of oxytetracycline twice at a 15-d interval caused a remission of the symptoms. These results confirmed the occurrence of RYD in Assam. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Fall-off rates of *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) and efficiency of the predator *Limnognus fossarum* (F.)

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The water strider *Limnognus fossarum* (F.) (Hemiptera: Gerridae) is common in wetland ricefields. It often feeds on brown planthoppers (BPH) that fall off the rice plants. We determined fall-off rates of the BPH and efficiency of *L. fossarum* in attacking those BPH that fell off.

BPH-resistant IR64 and susceptible TN 1 grown in the laboratory were used. The experimental arena consisted of a potted rice plant (35 d old) trimmed to five tillers and placed in a plastic container filled with water and enclosed in a cylindrical mylar cage (17 cm diameter, 50 cm high). The water level was kept at 1 cm above the brim of the pot.

In the fall-off study, 1-d-old BPH females were introduced into the experimental arena at densities of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 60, each replicated five times. BPH in the water were recorded 24 h later.

The predation rate of *L. fossarum* was measured in a different experiment replicated five times using the same BPH densities. We released a 1-d-old female *L. fossarum* inside the experimental arena containing 1-d-old BPH females. We recorded the BPH consumed after 24 h.

The number of BPH that fell off the plants was related to density (see figure). Fall-off was highest at density 60, and was significantly higher in IR64 than in

All of the fungicides significantly reduced neck B1 incidence. Chlobenthiazole proved most effective and reduced incidence by 85.7%, increasing yield by 13.9%. Soil application of edifenphos was the least effective (see table). □

Rate of fall-off of BPH and consumption by *L. fossarum* at different BPH densities.

TN1. The rate of BPH consumption by *L. fossarum* increased with density. The number of BPH attacked was significantly higher in IR64 than in TN1 at the higher densities.

Number of BPH consumed and fall-off were not correlated, however. The number consumed, especially at lower BPH densities, was generally higher than the number of those falling off. This indicates that the water strider did not only prey on BPH that fell into the water, but that it also attacked BPH on the plant. Consumption was higher with the resistant cultivar IR64, suggesting that the fall-off also increased BPH consumption by *L. fossarum*. □